

Tanzania's Financial Consumer Protection at the Crossroads: The Missing Role of Alternative Dispute Resolution

Joseph Falagamoja,

Dar es Salaam Tumaini University (DarTu), Tanzania.

Email: josephfalagamoja@gmail.com

Abstract:

The expansion of Tanzania's financial sector has led to an increase in disputes between banks and consumers, particularly regarding issues of fairness, transparency, and accountability. Although the Bank of Tanzania (Financial Consumer Protection) Regulations of 2019 provide for the determination of complaints, they do not integrate Alternative Dispute Resolution (ADR) mechanisms, such as mediation, conciliation, and arbitration. The position of this paper is that the integration of ADR into the framework for the resolution of consumer complaints will enhance the ways by which consumers are protected. Thus, this article examines the legal gaps and challenges within Tanzania's consumer protection framework, focusing on the absence of structured ADR procedures. Drawing on doctrinal and international standards, it argues that the lack of ADR integration not only limits access to justice but also hinders consumer's confidence in financial services. This article concludes by recommending regulatory reforms, including the establishment of an independent financial complaint desk, which will comply with international consumer protection guidelines and enhance awareness and fairness in financial dispute resolution.

Keywords: Financial Consumer, Banking, Bank of Tanzania, Alternative Dispute Resolution, Protection.

Suggested Citation: J. Falagamoja (2024), 'Tanzania's Financial Consumer Protection at the Crossroads: The Missing Role of Alternative Dispute Resolution,' *TzJMS*. Vol. 2. No. 1. pp. 59-67.

This work is licensed under the Creative Commons Attribution

International License (CC BY 4.0).

1. INTRODUCTION

The development of Tanzania's financial sector has contributed to the expansion of consumer access to banking products and services¹. However, this development has been accompanied by an increase in disputes between financial institutions and their clients, which is caused by unauthorized deductions, hidden charges, unfair lending practices, and poor customer redress.² Traditionally, consumers who are seeking remedies have relied on the formal court system, which is often more costly, delay, and procedurally technical³. Thus, through this situation, there is a need for having effective and affordable mechanisms that can ensure timely, less costly, and friendly procedures in the resolution of financial disputes.

The Bank of Tanzania, as a regulator in the financial sector in Tanzania, decided to come up with the Financial Consumer Protection Regulations, 2019, which were amended by the Bank of Tanzania (Financial Consumer Protection) (Amendment) Regulations, 2025, published as Government Notice No. 298 of 2025 on 23 May 2025. The main objective is to strengthen consumer protection and ensure redress mechanisms.⁴ One major issue is about Regulation 53, which gives power to the regulator bank to make a binding and conclusive determination on consumer complaints, without providing a clear avenue for independent procedures that will be used by the regulator bank to determine such matters or complaints.

This provision was widely criticized for undermining timely interventions to resolve complaints and impose sanctions against failure to comply with decisions of the Bank, which placed consumers in a weaker bargaining position.⁵ In reaction to the criticism, the regulator bank, that is the Bank of Tanzania, promulgated the Bank of Tanzania (Financial Consumer Protection) (Amendment) Regulations, 2025, published as Government Notice No. 298 of 2025 on 23 May 2025. The amendments of 2025 provided for the timely resolution of complaints made by consumers against financial service providers, as well as sanctions against financial services providers who fail to comply with the decisions of the Bank of Tanzania.⁶ Yet, the amendments did not expressly incorporate ADR mechanisms into the complaint handling process.

¹World Bank Group. (2013). *Tanzania Diagnostic Review of Consumer Protection and Financial Literacy: Volume 1. Key Findings and Recommendations*. Washington, DC: World Bank. Pg 6

²World Bank Group. (2013). *Tanzania Diagnostic Review of Consumer Protection and Financial Literacy: Volume 2. Comparison with Good Practices*. Washington, DC: World Bank. Pg 2

³Mashamba, C.J. (2014). *Alternative Dispute Resolution in Tanzania: Law and practice*, Mkuki na Nyota Publishers

⁴The Financial Consumer Protection Regulations, 2019, long title.

⁵ Ibid,

⁶Regulation 32, The Bank of Tanzania (Financial Consumer Protection) (Amendment) Regulations, 2025, published as Government Notice No. 298 of 2025 on 23 May 2025.

2. THE LEGAL FRAMEWORK FOR CONSUMER PROTECTION

The Bank of Tanzania Act CAP 197 R.E 2023, which was enacted in 2006 and has been revised in 2023, establishes the Bank of Tanzania as the central bank and the regulator of banks with the power to regulate, monitor, and supervise the function of banks and financial institutions.⁷ This supervisory role includes setting standards for how banks handle consumer complaints. The provision gives the banks legal authority to design an Alternative Dispute Resolution mechanism, such as mediation or conciliation, in the resolution of complaints, since effective dispute settlement falls within the proper regulation of banks. Thus, Section 70,⁸ authorizes the Bank of Tanzania as a regulator, to issue the Financial Consumer Protection Regulations, which outline how to protect consumers in different aspects of the services that financial institutions provide to their customers.⁹

The Bank of Tanzania (Financial Consumer Protection) Regulations 2019 and their amendments of 2025 were enacted to provide a framework for safeguarding the interests of financial consumers by promoting fairness, transparency, accountability, and responsible business practices within the banking sector.¹⁰ In the context of financial disputes between banks and consumers, these regulations serve as the principal legal assurance that define how complaints are to be managed at the institutional level and provide an alternative to purely judicial processes.

2.1 Internal complaint to the bank

The process begins when a customer has a dispute with a bank, such as unauthorized deductions, unfair charges, or loan related grievances. At this stage, the customer is required to report the complaint directly to the bank, either in writing, verbally, or electronically. This process is regarded as an internal complaint to the bank, which is covered under Regulations 42 to 49.¹¹ These provisions establish a sequential framework that reflects the initial stages of Alternative Dispute Resolution mechanisms, though not expressly labelled as such within the regulation.

Under Regulation 42(1),¹² a consumer may exercise his right to lodge a complaint against a financial service provider. Thus, a customer who is dissatisfied with a financial decision, service, or conduct must first submit a complaint directly to the respective financial service provider. In our view, this initial stage represents the first approach of Alternative

⁷Section 6 The Bank of Tanzania Act CAP 197 R.E 2023

⁸ Ibid, Section 70

⁹The Bank of Tanzania (Financial Consumer Protection) Regulations 2019

¹⁰The Bank of Tanzania (Financial Consumer Protection) Regulations, 2019, long title

¹¹Regulation 42-50 The Bank of Tanzania (Financial Consumer Protection) Regulations, 2019

¹²Ibid, Regulation 42 has been amended by Regulation 26 of the Bank of Tanzania (Financial Consumer Protection) (Amendment) Regulations, 2025, published as Government Notice No. 298 of 2025 on 23 May 2025.

Dispute Resolution, since it emphasizes internal complaint handling and encourages early settlement without court intervention. The financial service provider is required under Regulation 43 to acknowledge receipt of the complaint within a reasonable time and to resolve it.¹³ In practice, this process mirrors Alternative Dispute Resolution principles such as negotiation and conciliation, where dialogue and mutual understanding are encouraged before escalation. But the regulation did not provide for any procedure that a financial service provider has to follow during the settlement of the consumers' complaints, rather than that the provider is only required to notify the consumer of its decision in writing.¹⁴ Nevertheless, these regulations establish a step for redress, even if they do not expressly provide mediation, conciliation, or arbitration mechanisms, which are methods for alternative dispute settlement between the parties. This gap limits the efficiency of Alternative Dispute Resolution in practice, as consumers lack a formal platform for neutral facilitation before matters are administratively determined by a regulatory bank.

2.2 Escalation to the Bank of Tanzania

If the consumer remains dissatisfied with the financial service provider's determination, Regulation 29,¹⁵ allows the consumer to follow up on the matter with the regulatory bank, which is the Bank of Tanzania. The regulator bank then assumes a quasi-Alternative Dispute Resolution role by reviewing the complaint to determine whether the financial institution has complied with the principles of fairness, transparency, and consumer protection. Nevertheless, this procedure remains largely administrative and does not involve the use of an independent Alternative Dispute Resolution forum.

The finality of the regulator's determination is established under Regulation 53, which declares the decision to be binding and conclusive.¹⁶ This provision demonstrates the finality of regulatory administrative decisions and leaves no room for further negotiation, mediation, or arbitration. Although it ensures regulatory efficiency, this finality raises concern over procedural fairness applied to determine the complaint. The absence of Alternative Dispute Resolution with its flexibility effectively excludes opportunities for parties to engage in facilitated settlement or appeal to an independent Alternative Dispute Resolution body before litigation.

This position was emphasized in the case of *Emmanuel Simon Mshindo vs Bank of Africa Tanzania Limited*, where the court held that if a complaint remains unresolved, or if a

¹³Ibid, Regulation 43, has been amended by Regulation 27 of the Bank of Tanzania (Financial Consumer Protection) (Amendment) Regulations, 2025, published as Government Notice No. 298 of 2025 on 23 May 2025.

¹⁴Regulation 28 of the Bank of Tanzania (Financial Consumer Protection) (Amendment) Regulations, 2025, published as Government Notice No. 298 of 2025 on 23 May 2025.

¹⁵Ibid, Regulation 29

¹⁶Ibid, Regulation 53

consumer believes their rights have been violated in the manner the dispute was resolved, the proper legal remedy is to follow the procedures in the regulator's complaint handling procedures, including seeking revision from the governor, before instituting a suit in court. The court declared that the complainant in that case ought to have pursued revision before the governor and, if still dissatisfied, sought judicial review rather than filing a fresh commercial suit.¹⁷ This judgment illustrates how judicial review serves as the final safeguard for consumers under the Tanzanian system, but also highlights the limited options available, as it only reviews legality and procedure, not the substantive fairness of the bank's decision.

In practice, these provisions demonstrate that Tanzania's regulatory framework is not exhaustive in its use of Alternative Dispute Resolution mechanisms. The absence of formal Alternative Dispute Resolution procedures such as mediation or conciliation within the Bank of Tanzania framework deprives consumers and financial institutions of the opportunity to resolve disputes amicably and efficiently. In consequence, they decide to approach the court for redress.

3. STRENGTHS AND WEAKNESSES OF THE COMPLAINTS HANDLING AND REDRESS MECHANISM

Tanzania's financial consumer protection framework has several strengths. Firstly, it provides formal recognition of complaint handling as an essential component of financial regulation. The Bank of Tanzania (Financial Consumer Protection) Regulations, 2019 require financial institutions to establish internal mechanisms for receiving, recording, and addressing consumer complaints. This acknowledgment represents progress toward aligning Tanzania with international standards that emphasize the right to redress as a cornerstone of consumer protection. By mandating banks to handle complaints, the framework aims to provide consumers with a first point of contact that is accessible, relatively informal, and free from cost.

The second strength is the emphasis on transparency and disclosure obligations. Financial institutions are compelled to inform consumers of the procedures available for submitting complaints and to provide timelines for addressing them. This requirement enhances consumer awareness and promotes accountability by ensuring that banks cannot ignore or dismiss a consumer's grievances without due consideration. The complaints handling and redress mechanisms suffer from some weaknesses. The main concern is the lack of procedural clarity in how complaints are to be investigated and resolved. While the regulation imposes obligations on the banks to receive and determine complaints, it fails to provide detailed guidance on procedures to follow. This leaves banks

¹⁷Emmanuel Simon Mshindo vs Bank of Africa Tanzania Limited (Commercial Case No. 6729 of 2025) [2025] TZHCComD 206 p 5-6.

with high discretion, which can result in inconsistency, delay, or outcomes that favor financial institutions at the expense of consumers.

Another weakness is the absence of Alternative dispute resolution mechanisms within the redressing process. The regulations do not provide for mediation, conciliation, or arbitration. As a result, consumers who are dissatisfied with a bank's determination often face the difficult choice of accepting an unfavorable decision or resorting to a formal court process, which is a costly, slow, and complicated procedure. This undermines access to justice for lower-income consumers who lack the financial and legal support to litigate the disputes.

4. CHALLENGES IN RESOLVING BANKER-CUSTOMER DISPUTES

4.1 Absence of clear procedures

The Bank of Tanzania, its complaints are resolved by virtue of Regulation 53 of The Bank of Tanzania (Financial Consumer Protection) Regulations, 2019, which provides the power to make a final determination on consumer complaints. The law does not prescribe clear procedures or steps to be followed when resolving disputes. This regulatory gap means that banks may handle complaints differently, often relying on internal processes without formal mechanisms for mediation, conciliation, or arbitration. The absence of a standard procedure may reduce transparency and may limit fairness, as consumers are left without a clear pathway for redress. In the case of *Emmanuel Simon Mshindo vs Bank of Africa Tanzania Limited*, the court was of the view that the consumer had to follow the regulator bank's complaint handling procedures, including seeking a revision from the governor, before instituting a suit in court. The judgment noted that the plaintiff, being dissatisfied with the Bank of Tanzania desk's closure of his complaint, should have followed the statutory steps under the Regulations rather than filing a case directly in the court.

4.2 Party autonomy in consumer redress

One of the essential principles of Alternative dispute resolution is party autonomy, which ensures that the disputing parties actively participate in the process and have a role in shaping the resolution of their disputes. This principle also applies in resolving financial consumer disputes. However, the Tanzanian framework, as outlined in the Bank of Tanzania (Financial Consumer Protection) Regulations, 2019, does not expressly safeguard party autonomy.¹⁸ In *Emmanuel Simon Mshindo vs Bank of Africa Tanzania Limited*, parties were largely excluded from the process of determining the complaint lodged by the consumer. Thus, the court held that the Bank of Tanzania's complaint Desk

¹⁸The Bank of Tanzania (Financial Consumer Protection) Regulations, 2019

made determinations and closed disputes without affording the consumers meaningful involvement beyond the initial filing of forms.¹⁹

4.3 Lack of a legal representative

One of the critical gaps in the Bank of Tanzania (Financial Consumer Protection) Regulation, 2019, is the absence of a provision guaranteeing the right of parties to be represented by a legal counsel or advocate in the complaints process.²⁰ In practice, lawyers are restricted from participating in proceedings before the Bank of Tanzania's complaints desk. This limits the consumer's ability to present his case effectively in complex claims or defend their rights, especially when dealing with powerful financial institutions that possess greater legal and technical resources. The denial of legal representation undermines the principle of equality of fair dispute resolution, which is against the principle of natural justice.²¹ This problem was indirectly reflected in *Emmanuel Simon Mshindo vs Bank of Africa Tanzania Limited*, where the court observed that Bank of Tanzania and the parties were represented by an advocate or lawyer only after formal litigation had begun.²²

4.4 Lack of independent appeal mechanisms

The right to appeal is a fundamental safeguard in dispute resolution as it ensures fairness, accountability, and the correction of errors. Regulation 55 of The Bank of Tanzania (Financial Consumer Protection) Regulations, 2019, provides that if a complainant or financial service provider is dissatisfied with the regulator's determination, he may within seven days, request the Governor to revise the decision.²³ However, this revision process is conducted solely by the Governor, either by considering further written submissions or without requesting them.²⁴ This arrangement concentrates appellate authority in a single office, which undermines impartiality and raises concerns about the fairness of the determination. The lack of an independent appellate body creates the risk of biased or unbalanced outcomes, as the Governor is part of the same regulatory institution that made the initial determination.

The weaknesses of this Regulation were evident in the case of *Emmanuel Simon Mshindo vs Bank of Africa Tanzania Limited*, where the court emphasized that a complainant who is dissatisfied with the complaints desk's decision was obliged to request revision by the

¹⁹*Emmanuel Simon Mshindo vs Bank of Africa Tanzania Limited* (supra), 4-5.

²⁰The Bank of Tanzania (Financial Consumer Protection) Regulation, 2019

²¹Regulation 53(3), of The Bank of Tanzania (Financial Consumer Protection) Regulations 2019 has been amended by Regulation 32 of the Bank of Tanzania (Financial Consumer Protection) (Amendment) Regulations, 2025, published as Government Notice No. 298 of 2025 on 23 May 2025.

²²*Emmanuel Simon Mshindo vs Bank of Africa Tanzania Limited* (Commercial Case No. 6729 of 2025) [2025] TZHCComD 206 p 1-3

²³Regulation 55(1),

²⁴Regulation 55(2),

Governor before approaching the court²⁵. This left the plaintiff with no opportunity to present his grievance before an independent forum, demonstrating how the absence of a neutral appellate mechanism limits consumer protection.

4.5 Effectiveness of redress mechanisms

The effectiveness of ADR in resolving financial consumer disputes in Tanzania remains open to debate. Although the Bank of Tanzania (Financial Consumer Protection) Regulation, 2019 requires banks to establish complaint-handling mechanisms, the absence of explicit ADR procedures undermines fairness and consistency in practice. The effectiveness of the complaint handling procedure mostly depends on how banks interpret their obligations, which results in varied outcomes for consumers. While the legal and compliance officers of banks, can through informal negotiations play, useful roles in addressing minor disputes, especially those concerning customer relations, complex cases involving contractual interpretation or significant financial claims, may require expertise and the use of an ADR framework. Complex cases limit the utility of the current complaint's procedure.

4.6 Administrative or institutional challenges

Another significant institutional challenge in Tanzania's financial consumer protection framework is the lack of a legally established and independent body dedicated to resolving consumer complaints. The Bank of Tanzania laws and its regulations do not provide for the establishment of a specialized redress institution. Instead, complaints are handled administratively through "*Dawati la malalamiko*" (that is, complaints desk),²⁶ which operates as a department within the regulator itself rather than as an autonomous dispute resolution forum. This arrangement limits impartiality, as the same regulator that supervises financial institutions is also tasked with resolving disputes between consumers and those institutions. The absence of a distinct statutory body undermines the credibility of the process and leaves consumers with little confidence in the neutrality of outcomes.

This problem was evident in *Emmanuel Simon Mshindo vs Bank of Africa Tanzania Limited*, where the court noted that the plaintiff had referred his complaint to the Bank of Tanzania's Complaint Desk. Although the Desk issued directives, the dispute was later closed without ensuring compliance, leaving the consumer dissatisfied. The court stressed that the plaintiff should have sought revision before the Governor of the Bank of Tanzania, and if still dissatisfied, judicial review.²⁷ This shows that the system relies entirely on internal regulators' structures, without an independent body empowered by law to resolve disputes conclusively and fairly.

²⁵Ibid, p 4-5

²⁶The Bank of Tanzania (Financial Consumer Protection) Regulation, 2019.

²⁷*Emmanuel Simon Mshindo vs Bank of Africa Tanzania Limited* (Commercial Case No. 6729 of 2025) [2025] TZHCComD 206 p 6.

5. THE ROLE OF ALTERNATIVE DISPUTE RESOLUTION IN RESOLVING BANK-CUSTOMER COMPLAINTS

Alternative dispute resolution mechanisms have the potential role in enhancing financial dispute resolution in Tanzania by improving efficiency and reducing case backlogs, as alternative dispute resolution processes generally deliver outcomes faster than traditional court litigation. Alternative dispute resolution also promotes fairness and neutrality by allowing both banks and consumers to participate actively in reaching a mutually acceptable solution. Alternative dispute resolution is a more informal and flexible procedure that increases accessibility, especially for consumers with limited legal awareness. Moreover, Alternative dispute resolution is fully confidential. This will help to preserve the reputation of financial institutions while protecting consumer privacy. Additionally, alternative dispute resolution is cost effective compared to formal litigation, reducing legal costs for both parties. Collectively, these advantages demonstrate that alternative dispute resolution can significantly improve the quality and effectiveness of financial dispute resolution in Tanzania.

6. CONCLUSION

Advancing Alternative Dispute Resolution in Tanzania's financial sector is essential not only for ensuring consumer protection but also for promoting trust, efficiency, and accountability within the financial system. By addressing existing legal and institutional weaknesses and showing comparative best practices, Tanzania can establish a more inclusive, transparent, and effective dispute resolution framework that meets the needs of its financial consumers and strengthens the overall justice system. To resolve the problems examined in this paper, the Bank of Tanzania (Financial Consumer Protection) Regulations have to be amended to explicitly provide for Alternative Dispute Resolution mechanisms such as mediation, conciliation, and arbitration. resolution. There is a need to review and strengthen the regulatory framework to integrate Alternative Dispute Resolution into complaint handling procedures. The regulator bank should issue specific Alternative Dispute Resolution guidelines to financial institutions, setting out clear timelines, procedures, and fairness standards. Furthermore, banks should be required to adopt internal mechanisms that prioritize negotiation, conciliation, and mediation before escalation to the regulator.